

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP3.14

Workpackage 3

Responsible Partner: WBVR (NL)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018 (BIOPIGEE 01/01/2020)
Duration	60 Months (BIOPIGEE 36 months)

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP21-WP3.14 Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers/biofilm		
Project Acronym	JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE		
Author	Renate Hakze – van der Honing, Wim van der Poel (WBVR)		
Other contributors	-		
Due month of the report	M50		
Actual submission month	M58		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 14-Oct-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Confidential until publication.....		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s): via publication		

BIOPIGEE

Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers/biofilm

Participating country

NL (WBVR)

Objective

The objective was to test if HEV is more stable for disinfectants when it is present in a *Salmonella* biofilm.

Background

Every year, worldwide, 20 million people become infected with Hepatitis E virus (HEV), of which 3 million are acute cases and 57000 cases are fatal, according to the World Health Organization. HEV causes liver inflammation, fever and jaundice in humans and chronic HEV infections have been reported in immunocompromised individuals. HEV genotypes 3 and 4 are zoonotic, and for these genotypes the major animal reservoirs are supposedly domestic and wild pigs. The main route of HEV transmission to humans in Europe is then through consumption of contaminated pork meat or pork products. But pigs can also shed HEV into the environment, in which the virus can stay infective for months. Such environmental spread will lead to contamination of drinking water and crops. In European countries more than 50% of the pig farms may be affected and HEV seroprevalence within these farms can be over 80%. Given the assumption that HEV could survive longer in *Salmonella* biofilms, leading to a higher prevalence of viable HEV in environments with *Salmonella* biofilm formations, the objective of this research task was to test for HEV survival in such samples. To confirm the first assumption the work was started with a study to assess the effectivity of disinfectant to reduce HEV viability and an investigation whether HEV is more prevalent in the environmental samples contaminated with *Salmonella*. In case there is no correlation between the actual prevalences of HEV and *Salmonella* in such samples, there may be very limited added value on testing the stability of HEV in *Salmonella* biofilm environmental samples.

Methods

Disinfection of HEV

Almost all the pig farms in the Netherlands use MS megaDes Novo (0,75%) to disinfect their stables. In user dilution, it contains 150 gr/l Glutaraldehyde and 110 gr/l Quaternaire ammonium.

Positive A HEV-positive cell-culture sample was incubated in a ten-fold dilution series for 5 minutes at room temperature with the prescribed user dilution of MS MegaDes Novo before it was used as an inoculum on a cell culture monolayer. The same HEV-positive sample without the pre-treatment with the disinfectant was used as a control in the cell culture system.

Before testing whether HEV is more stable for disinfectants when it is present in a *Salmonella* biofilm sample, it was decided to first study if HEV is more prevalent in the presence of such *Salmonella* biofilm formations. For this purpose we studied 110 faecal swine samples for the presence of both salmonella and HEV. In addition, we collected environmental samples on a pig farm after the disinfection procedure and tested the samples for the presence of *Salmonella* and HEV.

Sampling Method in the stables

The walls, floors and feed bowl in pig pens where biofilms can be expected were wiped with electrostatic dust collectors (EDCs). The drinking nipple was wiped with a swab. After collection, the EDCs were directly tested or stored in a 50 ml tube (Greiner) at -80°C until the procedure was continued. Medium (5 ml) was added to each tube and incubated 1.5 hours while rolling at room temperature. After testing using HEV PCR, supernatants obtained from HEV-positive cloths were used to perform cell culture propagation as described below.

Cell culture

A fresh liver, obtained from a young piglet was perfused with Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F12) (Gibco) until most of the blood was flushed away. After cutting the liver into small pieces, it was inoculated with and incubated in 0,1% collagenase IV in DMEM/F12 for 1 hour at 37 °C. Liver cells were collected and detached from each other using a 70µm cell strainer. The cell suspension was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1200rpm and the pellet was washed once with DMEM/F12 (Gibco). The liver cells were cultured in growth medium containing DMEM/F12 with 10 % Fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1 % anti/anti (Gibco) and 40ul/ml suppl-B (Gibco) in a T150 culture flask coated with Collagen I. The flasks were incubated with 12ml 100ug/ml Collagen 1 in 0.02M HAC. After two hours these were washed with PBS and dried for 4 hours or used directly. The next day the cells were washed stringently to get rid of cells other than hepatocytes. As soon as the cells had been growing confluent for a couple of days, these were used for infection experiments or were frozen in liquid nitrogen for later use.

Primary hepatocytes were seeded in growth medium on a 6 wells plate format coated with Collagen I. When an almost confluent monolayer of the hepatocytes was observed, the cells were inoculated with a 1ml test sample. After an incubation of 6 hours the inoculate was removed and the cells were washed with DMEM/F12 prior to adding 2ml of the maintenance medium containing DMEM/F12 with 2 % Fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1 % anti/anti (Gibco) and 40ul/ml suppl-B (Gibco). The medium was refreshed for about 50% each 2nd or 3rd day depending on the day of inoculation. Six days after inoculation, a sample was collected for analysing with real-time rtPCR to detect HEV.

RNA isolation and Real-time RT-PCR

RNA isolation was carried out using the Quick pathogen kit (Zymo Research), 150µl sample was added to 150µl DNA/RNA shield and performed according to the manual. The DNA/RNA was eluted in 50µl elution buffer. The HEV RNA was amplified on the LC480 (Roche diagnostic) machine with the real-time rtPCR of Jothikumar et al. (2006) using the TaqMan Fast Virus 1-step Master Mix (applied biosystems). The *Salmonella* was amplified on the AB7500 (Applied biosystems) machine with an in-house PCR protocol

Results

Disinfection of HEV

After a 5-minute incubation of the samples with MS MegaDes Novo we were not able to culture the virus anymore in the hepatocyte cell culture system.

Table 1. 110 faecal samples were tested for the presence of salmonella and HEV

Total samples tested	110
Positive HEV	34 (Ct<40)
Positive <i>Salmonella</i>	21
Positive <i>Salmonella</i> and HEV	9

Table 2. Environmental samples on a pig farm tested for HEV and Salmonella

Environmental samples	N	HEV-pos	HEV-neg	<i>Salmonella</i>-pos	<i>Salmonella</i>-neg
Floor	67	4	63	44	23
Wall	67	2	65	47	18
Feed bowl	75	6	69	39	30
Drink nipple	75	2	73	26	47

Conclusion

A 5-minute incubation with MS MegaDes Novo seems to be sufficient to completely inactivate HEV. The presence of HEV after disinfection therefore is unlikely to be due to the use of an invalid disinfection agent. From the earlier mentioned results we can conclude that there is no correlation between the prevalences of *Salmonella* and HEV in pig farm environmental samples. Survival of HEV in a pig farm, with or without the presence of *Salmonella* is more likely to be due to inaccurate cleaning practices. The Floor and the feed bowl showed the highest levels of HEV contamination and therefore seem to be the most likely the source of HEV re-infection.

Future work

Not really indicated at this point but in this work we did not test for different *Salmonella* strains. It could be argued that there may be differences for different *Salmonella* strains. As indicated we could discriminate for different *Salmonella* biofilm formations and test for HEV prevalences in the samples with different *Salmonella* strains. Subsequently the developed viability test could be used to test for viable HEV.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.